
THE ROLE OF SAFE TOURISM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PHILOSOPHICAL THINKING OF SOCIETY IN UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8262899>

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Abstract

By the new century, every country has realized that its level of socio-economic development is related to tourism. In the article, taking into account these aspects, the issues of developing the safe tourism industry in Uzbekistan are put forward. It reflects the philosophical significance of the reforms being carried out in the field, views related to ensuring the safety of foreign and domestic tourists coming to our country. Safe tourism is a kind of integrated system in updating the philosophical thinking of society, and tourists have a special role in this regard. The fact that tourism objects have opened wide opportunities for the development of the philosophical thinking of citizens in the society, for the people to live on the basis of modern ideas and innovations has been revealed in connection with the development of the philosophical consciousness.

Key words

tourism industry, safe tourism, foreign and local tourists, state, philosophical consciousness, philosophical worldview, society, spirituality, people, citizens, values, tourism objects.

The processes of development of socio-philosophical thinking in new Uzbekistan directly serve the problems of society in the field of safe tourism. This shows that necessary conditions will be created for the large-scale development of the tourism sector and the acceleration of changes in social and economic life. Today, increasing the attention of various countries in the world to the field of safe tourism has become a demand of the time. The development of this industry is a process directly related to the historical heritage and culture of New Uzbekistan. Therefore, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 939 dated November 23, 2017 "On measures to ensure safe tourism in the cities of Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva and Shahrisabz in 2017-2020" was adopted, and on this basis, the concept of providing safe tourism was approved. In order to ensure the execution of the decision, the activities of the internal affairs bodies on ensuring the safety of tourism have been improved. On the basis of this decision, activity of

special tourism situation centers was organized in the IIB of Tashkent region, Tashkent city, Bukhara, Samarkand, Khorezm, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions. They are engaged in constantly monitoring the state of safe tourism, informing local and foreign tourists about possible dangers in real time, helping to protect their rights and legal interests, and ensuring security in the historical places of our nation.

Currently, departments for ensuring safe tourism have been established in the internal affairs departments of Tashkent region, Tashkent city, Bukhara, Samarkand, Khorezm, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions, and the heads of these departments have been appointed. They, in turn, are considered as deputy heads of regional IIB, and serve to ensure the organization and safety of new tourism facilities in the regions. Young employees who have perfect knowledge of foreign languages and who have mastered the rich spiritual and philosophical outlook of our ancestors have been employed in these newly established departments. The reason is that the head of our state is supporting the development of the tourism sector, paying special attention to the fact that all the objects of the tourism sector are regions that reflect the values, spirituality, moral principles, and historical heritage of our people. As Sh. Mirziyoev noted, " We want the people of the world to get to know our country closely, to see the rich history and culture of our people with their own eyes." Tourism opportunities play an important role in this regard. Therefore, we are paying serious attention to the development of tourism in our country, and it is giving its results " [1]. It is natural that all this will serve for the future prosperous life of our country, the feeling of pride of our people in the history of their ancestors, and will serve to convey them carefully to the future. For this purpose, our country has a priceless spiritual heritage, imbued with high philosophical thinking and wisdom formed historically.

its ancient history and philosophical values of the past, Pakistan has always been the center of attention of the peoples of the world. Therefore, ensuring the safety of tourists visiting our country today, continuously introducing them to our interesting culture is aimed at the development of tomorrow. In addition, it is important to expand the philosophical outlook of foreigners about New Uzbekistan, to form positive views of our history in their minds [2]. In this regard, the achievement of modern thinking of every citizen in our country is a unique achievement, and their passion for world tourism is also increasing.

It is important to control the safety of tourists visiting our country from foreign countries and staying in our country for a certain period, as well as the legality of their rights. When using the means of transport in our country, in the

process of communication with the population, it is necessary to respect the issues related to nationality, to deal with tourists without lowering their honor and value. Also, the field of safe tourism is important in constantly improving the culture of tourism service providers among our people, keeping track of foreign tourists who have come to our country, and forming a single information base of state and non-state organizations. Increasing the convenience of transport services for foreign and domestic tourists in the implementation of tourism in Uzbekistan is also a special feature. That's why posters, signs and indicators serving modern tourism are being installed in Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva, Shahrisabz and other cities in transport infrastructures and service facilities. These in turn ensure that tourists reach their destinations safely and quickly.

The rules of stay in our country, visa and registration processes will be explained to tourists visiting from abroad through the mobile application by employees of safe tourism departments established in New Uzbekistan. They are constantly informed about the interesting destinations of Uzbekistan, their directions, as well as the nearest internal affairs body base points and medical institutions. In this mobile application, a tourist can send a message to the law enforcement authorities about getting into a difficult situation or write an appeal to the consular office of his country[3]. In Uzbekistan, an electronic information system "E-guest" was introduced, which allows for the formation of a database for tourists arriving at each hotel in the field of ensuring the safety of the place of residence of foreign tourists, accommodation in hotels and providing services to them. This system is also closely related to the activities of the employees of the safe tourism sector, and serves for the tourists to stay overnight in the hotel of their choice, to plan in advance to visit nearby pilgrimage sites. The entrance to the hotels is under video surveillance day and night and is designed to ensure the safety of tourists. In addition, a single hardware and software complex "Safe tourism" has been introduced, and through this, the biero will quickly help the tourist to find the person responsible if someone acts inappropriately or pressures them, and to determine their identity. This allows for video surveillance, continuous data analysis and automatic processing. Receives and registers reports of violations and incidents related to tourists. The development and installation of requirements for special technical equipment for individual protection of tourists in the field of ensuring the safety of local tourists and official foreign delegations visiting tourist attractions and organizing evening entertainment programs also has a positive effect. At these events, foreign and domestic tourists' perceptions of our country and the rich spiritual heritage left to us by our ancestors are given. It is

intended to increase their philosophical outlook on changes in society, to strengthen their respect for our national values [4].

In order to increase the potential of safe tourism in our country, to turn tourism demonstration objects and places of pilgrimage into crime-free areas, raising the legal and philosophical outlook of the local population is being carried out. Protection of the rights and freedoms and legal interests of foreign and local tourists in each region of Uzbekistan, as well as ensuring the safety of high-ranking guests and representatives of delegations at international events held in the region are being effectively organized. Activities in the spiritual field are systematically organized for tourists, and they are developing their knowledge about the priceless masterpieces of philosophical thought in the land of Uzbekistan, as well as creating works about the saints and scholars who grew out of this land.

The number of tourists visiting Uzbekistan has been increasing in recent years. This requires the creation of all opportunities for the effective use of the tourist potential of each region, especially the provision of security. Therefore, the number of tourists visiting the Samarkand region and the indicators of ensuring the safety of tourists by the employees of the regional administration have increased significantly. In particular, the visit of local and foreign tourists to the region during the 12 months of 2022 was as follows;

- the total number of tourists is 5 million 300 thousand, and the flow of tourists compared to 2021 (2 million 229 thousand) is 3 million 10 thousand or 131.4%;

- the flow of foreign tourists amounted to 800,000, compared to 2021 (119,000) by 681,000 or 572.3%;

- the flow of domestic tourists amounted to 4 million 500 thousand people, which increased by 240 thousand people or 114.3% compared to 2021 (2 million 100 thousand).

In 2021, 56 thousand 212 tourists from a total of 137 foreign countries visited the region, while in 2022, 197 588 tourists from a total of 168 countries (32.3 percent more) (251.5 percent more) visited the region.

Also, in 2021, a total of 2,047 guests as part of 160 official delegations visited the region, and in 2022, 3,642 guests as part of 127 official delegations visited the region, and this indicator also increased to 77.9%.

In addition, in 2021, 62,788 foreign tourists visited the region on a one-day visit, and in 2022, this figure was 610,000, and the flow of tourists visiting the Samarkand region on a one-day visit increased almost 10 times [5].

In the past two years, the employees of the Safe Tourism Department of the Samarkand region have effectively organized the reception, security and monitoring of the representatives of the delegation, and no unpleasant situations were allowed during the visits. In addition, as a result of the effective organization of preventive and promotional activities to ensure public safety and increase the culture of hospitality to tourists in historical monuments and shrines, tourist streets and avenues, not a single crime and offense against foreign tourists was allowed, and no accident related to them was allowed. and no cases of sudden death were reported.

In 2021, a total of 468 offenders were detected in the objects of visitation and adjacent areas by the prevention inspectors of the IIB of Samarkand region, and in 2022, the indicators in the direction of administrative operations reached 857 and increased by 83.1%.

, 36 proposals and 4 proposals were made to official organizations and local government bodies, administrations of historical monuments and shrines to prevent crime and create additional amenities for tourists in places, markets, streets and avenues, historical monuments and shrines and their adjacent areas. submissions were made.

In addition, in order to prevent crimes and violations that may be committed against tourists, to improve the culture and hospitality of the population, meetings and roundtables are held on site, and propaganda is being carried out in the mass media.

These works serve to increase the flow of tourists in our country, to hold international events peacefully, to ensure public safety and the safety of high-ranking guests. Ensuring safe tourism will help all citizens of our country to visit pilgrimages on a large scale, and the employees of regional departments will provide decent service for human dignity.

As a result of the reforms implemented in new Uzbekistan, tourists will be recognized as "the city of Samarkand - the tourism center of the Turkic world and Central Asia" in 2022, and the city of Samarkand will be turned into a free tourist zone, and the region will be allowed to enter and exit freely through aviation, railway and highway checkpoints. contributed to its development. This increases the flow of tourists visiting our country, in turn, to strengthen the measures aimed at ensuring their safety, and imposes more responsibility on the employees of the Department of Safe Tourism of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Samarkand region.

Accelerating the activities of tourist centers in New Uzbekistan, conducting their future work in a more popular and open manner requires a unique philosophical and economic consciousness. In this regard, it is the goal of our country to further raise the image of our country as a "Safe Zone" based on the development of new innovative plans aimed at increasing the tourist coverage of all tourist facilities. For this purpose, more consistent digitization of work to ensure the safety of tourists visiting Uzbekistan, reducing the human factor will gain positive importance. In order to ensure that work in this regard is more effective, maps have been developed on the ways of rational use of all available opportunities, and they are distinguished by the fact that the indicators are updated every year, and changes in the field are focused on the interests of the people.

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